

A COMPUTER PROGRAM FOR THE CALCULATION OF THE ELASTIC PROPERTIES FOR MULTI-LAYERED FIBER-REINFORCED LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

In this work, the classical lamination theory has been used to develop a computer program for the determination of the stress-strain relations of the unidirectional and random fiber-reinforced multi-layered composite materials. In this program, the forces and moments (N_x , N_y , N_{xy} , M_x , M_y , M_{xy}) applied to the laminate can be given and strains and curvatures (ϵ_x , ϵ_y , γ_{xy} , κ_x , κ_y , κ_{xy}) are obtained, or vice versa. The user can choose between unidirectional or random fiber-reinforced laminates.

This interactive and user-friendly computer program has been written in GWBasic language and can be used on IBM PC/XT/AT or IBM compatible computers. This paper describes the details of this software.

Keywords: fiber-reinforced laminated composites, classical lamination theory, computer aided design.

1. INTRODUCTION

Materials are generally classified as metals, ceramics and organic materials. These three groups have some advantages and disadvantages compared to each other. Beside these groups, materials can be combined on a macroscopic scale, either to create new properties or to combine the properties in one material. We call these combined materials as composites [1]. Composite materials also classified into different groups. Fiber-reinforced composite materials are the most attractive group because of their high load bearing capacity. Fiber-reinforced composite materials are usually built of laminae which are plied up oriented at different directions. Compared to isotropic materials longer and more tedious mathematical operations are necessary to determine their stress-strain relations. Classical lamination theory is mostly used for these calculations and this theory is also used in this study.

The goal of this work is to create a user-friendly, fast and reliable software for persons who work with fiber-reinforced composite materials but have only basic engineering knowledge.

2. MACROMECHANICAL BEHAVIOR OF A LAMINA

2.1. Stress-Strain Relations and the Stiffness Matrix for Anisotropic Materials

The mechanical properties of fiber-reinforced composites are anisotropic and the required number of constants to define the elastic stress-strain relationship are much more than isotropic materials. (In isotropic materials only two constants are enough to define the material: E, ν). If the contracted notations ($\sigma_1=\sigma_{11}, \sigma_2=\sigma_{22}, \sigma_3=\sigma_{33}, \sigma_4=\tau_{23}, \sigma_5=\tau_{31}, \sigma_6=\tau_{12}$ and $\epsilon_1=\epsilon_{11}, \epsilon_2=\epsilon_{22}, \epsilon_3=\epsilon_{33}, \epsilon_4=\gamma_{23}, \epsilon_5=\gamma_{31}, \epsilon_6=\gamma_{12}$) are used then stress and strain relation in the elastic region can be written as

$$\sigma_i = C_{ij} \cdot \epsilon_j \quad (i, j = 1 \dots 6) \quad (1)$$

$$\epsilon_i = S_{ij} \cdot \sigma_j \quad (2)$$

where C_{ij} is the stiffness matrix and S_{ij} is the compliance matrix. Since a fiber-reinforced lamina has three symmetric planes it is an orthotropic material (orthogonal anisotropic). So the number of independent constants are only 9 [2].

$$\begin{bmatrix} \sigma_1 \\ \sigma_2 \\ \sigma_3 \\ \sigma_4 \\ \sigma_5 \\ \sigma_6 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} C_{11} & C_{12} & C_{13} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ C_{12} & C_{22} & C_{23} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ C_{13} & C_{23} & C_{33} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & C_{44} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & C_{55} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & C_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \epsilon_1 \\ \epsilon_2 \\ \epsilon_3 \\ \epsilon_4 \\ \epsilon_5 \\ \epsilon_6 \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

Simple uniaxial tension or shear tests can be used to obtain the above constants with the help of elastic properties. So for an orthotropic material, the compliance matrix components in terms of the engineering constants are

$$S_{ij} = \begin{bmatrix} 1/E_1 & -\nu_{21}/E_2 & -\nu_{31}/E_3 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -\nu_{12}/E_1 & 1/E_2 & -\nu_{32}/E_3 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -\nu_{13}/E_1 & -\nu_{23}/E_2 & 1/E_3 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1/G_{23} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1/G_{31} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1/G_{12} \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

Stiffness matrix can be obtained by the $C_{ij} = (S_{ij})^{-1}$ transformation [1]. Using micromechanical models the material engineering constants ($E_1, E_2, \nu_{12}, G_{12}$ etc.) can be determined with the help of the fiber and matrix properties ($E_f, E_m, \nu_f, \nu_m, G_f$ and G_m) and with the volume fractions of these constituents (ν_f and ν_m).

2.2. Plane Stress in Orthotropic Laminae

Since the fiber-reinforced laminae are thin, plane stress condition ($\sigma_3=0, \sigma_4=0, \sigma_5=0$) is acceptable. In this case the number of constants can be further reduced and a smaller Q_{ij} matrix (3x3) can be used instead of the 6x6 matrix. So the Hooke's law can be written as,

$$\begin{bmatrix} \sigma_1 \\ \sigma_2 \\ \sigma_6 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} Q_{11} & Q_{12} & 0 \\ Q_{12} & Q_{22} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & Q_{66} \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_1 \\ \varepsilon_2 \\ \varepsilon_6 \end{bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

In Equation 5, the number of independent constants are 4 and their expression with the help of the engineering constants are as follows,

$$\begin{aligned} Q_{11} &= \frac{E_1}{1 - \nu_{12} \cdot \nu_{21}} & Q_{12} &= \frac{\nu_{12} \cdot E_2}{1 - \nu_{12} \cdot \nu_{21}} \\ Q_{22} &= \frac{E_2}{1 - \nu_{12} \cdot \nu_{21}} & Q_{66} &= G_{12} \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

Figure 1. Unidirectionally reinforced lamina

2.3. Stress-Strain Relations for a Lamina of Arbitrary Orientation

The principal directions of material (orthotropic) may not coincide with the direction of stresses. In this case relations on different axes can be calculated by the help of the transformation matrix (T_{ij}).

$$[T] = \begin{bmatrix} \cos^2\theta & \sin^2\theta & 2\sin\theta\cos\theta \\ \sin^2\theta & \cos^2\theta & -2\sin\theta\cos\theta \\ -\sin\theta\cos\theta & \sin\theta\cos\theta & \cos^2\theta - \sin^2\theta \end{bmatrix} \quad (7)$$

If the axes of stress (x and y) do not coincide with the principal material directions (1 and 2) then stress-strain relation can be written as

$$\begin{bmatrix} \sigma_x \\ \sigma_y \\ \tau_{xy} \end{bmatrix} = [T]^{-1} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} \sigma_1 \\ \sigma_2 \\ \tau_{12} \end{bmatrix} = [\bar{Q}] \cdot \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_x \\ \varepsilon_y \\ \gamma_{xy} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \bar{Q}_{11} & \bar{Q}_{12} & \bar{Q}_{16} \\ \bar{Q}_{12} & \bar{Q}_{22} & \bar{Q}_{26} \\ \bar{Q}_{16} & \bar{Q}_{26} & \bar{Q}_{66} \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_x \\ \varepsilon_y \\ \gamma_{xy} \end{bmatrix} \quad (8)$$

where, \bar{Q}_{ij} matrix denotes the transformed reduced stiffnesses

$$\begin{aligned}
\bar{Q}_{11} &= Q_{11} \cdot \cos^4\theta + 2(Q_{12} + 2Q_{66})\sin^2\theta \cdot \cos^2\theta + Q_{22} \cdot \sin^4\theta \\
\bar{Q}_{12} &= (Q_{11} + Q_{22} - 4Q_{66})\sin^2\theta \cdot \cos^2\theta + Q_{12} \cdot (\sin^4\theta + \cos^4\theta) \\
\bar{Q}_{22} &= Q_{11} \cdot \sin^4\theta + 2(Q_{12} + 2Q_{66})\sin^2\theta \cdot \cos^2\theta + Q_{22} \cdot \cos^4\theta \\
\bar{Q}_{16} &= (Q_{11} - Q_{12} - 2Q_{66})\sin\theta \cdot \cos^3\theta + (Q_{12} - Q_{22} + 2Q_{66})\sin^3\theta \cdot \cos\theta \\
\bar{Q}_{26} &= (Q_{11} - Q_{12} - 2Q_{66})\sin^3\theta \cdot \cos\theta + (Q_{12} - Q_{22} + 2Q_{66})\sin\theta \cdot \cos^3\theta \\
\bar{Q}_{66} &= (Q_{11} + Q_{22} - 2Q_{12} - 2Q_{66})\sin^2\theta \cdot \cos^2\theta + Q_{66} \cdot (\sin^4\theta + \cos^4\theta)
\end{aligned}
\tag{9}$$

Figure 2. Positive rotation of principal material axes from arbitrary xy axes

3. MACROMECHANICAL BEHAVIOR OF A LAMINATE

3.1. Classical Lamination Theory

A laminate which consists of two or more laminae behaves like a structural element. Laminae in a laminate can be oriented in different directions. Classical lamination theory embodies a collection of stress and deformation hypotheses. By use of this theory, we can consistently proceed from the basic building block, the lamina, to the end result, a structural laminate [2].

3.2. Stress-Strain Behavior of a Lamina

The stress-strain relation in the principal material directions of the orthotropic lamina under plane stress condition is given in Equation 5. Stresses in the arbitrary axes in the lamina plane can be calculated with Equation 8. The stress-strain relation for the k^{th} layer of a multi-layered laminate can be written as

$$\{\sigma\}_k = [\bar{Q}]_k \cdot \{\varepsilon\}_k
\tag{10}$$

3.3. Stress-Strain Behavior of a Laminate

Extension and bending stiffnesses of the laminate should be known to determine the stress-strain relation through the thickness of the laminate. The assumptions made to evaluate the mechanical behavior of the laminate are as follows:

- a) The laminate is presumed to be infinitesimally thin as well as non-shear deformable, the laminate acts as a single layer.
- b) The surface perpendicular to the mid-surface remains as a plane when the laminate undergoes deformations. In other words there are no shear strains in planes perpendicular to the middle surface, that is,

$$\gamma_{xz} = \gamma_{yz} = 0 \quad (11)$$

where z is the direction of the normal to the middle surface.

c) The thickness remains constant so that the strain perpendicular to the middle surface is ignored,

$$\epsilon_z = 0 \quad (12)$$

The stresses in the k^{th} layer can be expressed in terms of the laminate middle surface strains and curvatures as

$$\begin{bmatrix} \sigma_x \\ \sigma_y \\ \tau_{xy} \end{bmatrix}_k = \begin{bmatrix} \bar{Q}_{11} & \bar{Q}_{12} & \bar{Q}_{16} \\ \bar{Q}_{12} & \bar{Q}_{22} & \bar{Q}_{26} \\ \bar{Q}_{16} & \bar{Q}_{26} & \bar{Q}_{66} \end{bmatrix}_k \cdot \begin{bmatrix} \epsilon_x^p \\ \epsilon_y^p \\ \gamma_{xy}^p \end{bmatrix} + z \cdot \begin{bmatrix} \kappa_x \\ \kappa_y \\ \kappa_{xy} \end{bmatrix} \quad (13)$$

Figure 3. Geometry of deformation in the xz plane

3.4. Resultant Laminate Forces and Moments

The resultant forces and moments acting on a laminate are obtained by integration of the stresses in each lamina through the laminate thickness.

$$N_x = \int_{-t/2}^{t/2} \sigma_x \cdot dz \quad M_x = \int_{-t/2}^{t/2} \sigma_x \cdot z \cdot dz \quad (14)$$

N_x is a force per unit length of the cross section of the laminate as shown in Figure 4. Similarly, M_x is a moment per unit length as shown in Figure 5.

Figure 4. In-plane forces on a flat laminate

Figure 5. Moments on a flat laminate

$$\begin{bmatrix} N_x \\ N_y \\ N_{xy} \end{bmatrix} = \sum_{k=1}^N \begin{bmatrix} \bar{Q}_{11} & \bar{Q}_{12} & \bar{Q}_{16} \\ \bar{Q}_{12} & \bar{Q}_{22} & \bar{Q}_{26} \\ \bar{Q}_{16} & \bar{Q}_{26} & \bar{Q}_{66} \end{bmatrix}_k \begin{bmatrix} z_k \\ \int_{z_{k-1}}^{z_k} \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_x^o \\ \varepsilon_y^o \\ \gamma_{xy}^o \end{bmatrix} dz \\ z_{k-1} \end{bmatrix} + \int_{z_{k-1}}^{z_k} \begin{bmatrix} \kappa_x \\ \kappa_y \\ \kappa_{xy} \end{bmatrix} z \cdot dz \quad (15)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} M_x \\ M_y \\ M_{xy} \end{bmatrix} = \sum_{k=1}^N \begin{bmatrix} \bar{Q}_{11} & \bar{Q}_{12} & \bar{Q}_{16} \\ \bar{Q}_{12} & \bar{Q}_{22} & \bar{Q}_{26} \\ \bar{Q}_{16} & \bar{Q}_{26} & \bar{Q}_{66} \end{bmatrix}_k \begin{bmatrix} z_k \\ \int_{z_{k-1}}^{z_k} \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_x^o \\ \varepsilon_y^o \\ \gamma_{xy}^o \end{bmatrix} z \cdot dz \\ z_{k-1} \end{bmatrix} + \int_{z_{k-1}}^{z_k} \begin{bmatrix} \kappa_x \\ \kappa_y \\ \kappa_{xy} \end{bmatrix} z^2 \cdot dz \quad (16)$$

z_k and z_{k-1} are the thickness coordinates on z direction, note that $z_0 = -t/2$ (Figure 6). These forces and moments do not depend on z but are functions of x and y . ε_x , ε_y , γ_{xy} , κ_x , κ_y , κ_{xy} are not functions of z . These values belong to the middle surface. So can be moved out of the summation signs. Thus, Equation 15 and Equation 16 can be written as

$$\begin{bmatrix} N_x \\ N_y \\ N_{xy} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} A_{11} & A_{12} & A_{16} \\ A_{12} & A_{22} & A_{26} \\ A_{16} & A_{26} & A_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_x^o \\ \varepsilon_y^o \\ \gamma_{xy}^o \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} B_{11} & B_{12} & B_{16} \\ B_{12} & B_{22} & B_{26} \\ B_{16} & B_{26} & B_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \kappa_x \\ \kappa_y \\ \kappa_{xy} \end{bmatrix} \quad (17)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} M_x \\ M_y \\ M_{xy} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} B_{11} & B_{12} & B_{16} \\ B_{12} & B_{22} & B_{26} \\ B_{16} & B_{26} & B_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_x^o \\ \varepsilon_y^o \\ \gamma_{xy}^o \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} D_{11} & D_{12} & D_{16} \\ D_{12} & D_{22} & D_{26} \\ D_{16} & D_{26} & D_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \kappa_x \\ \kappa_y \\ \kappa_{xy} \end{bmatrix} \quad (18)$$

where, the A_{ij} is the extensional stiffness matrix, the B_{ij} is the coupling stiffness matrix and the D_{ij} is the bending stiffness matrix. The B_{ij} implies the coupling between bending and extension of a laminate. Thus, it is impossible to pull on a laminate that has B_{ij} terms, without causing a bending and/or twisting at the same time [2].

Figure 6. Geometry of n-layered laminate

4. DETERMINING OF FORCES AND DEFLECTIONS WITH COMPUTER

The flow chart of the computer program which is prepared by using the classical lamination theory is given in Appendix [3].

The principal laminate axes can be chosen as the axes of the first lamina of laminate or arbitrary axes can be defined. After entering the number of laminae and their thicknesses, the angle between the principal laminate axes and fiber orientation of lamina is given. If the random fiber-reinforced type (mat) is chosen this information is not needed. A random fiber-reinforced lamina is assumed to be a 38-layered laminate with symmetrical fiber orientations changing from 0° to 180° .

Material properties of each lamina can be given as $(E_1, E_2, G_{12}, \nu_{12})$ or by the elastic properties of its fiber and matrix ($E_1, E_2, G_{12}, \nu_{12}$ are calculated by using the micromechanical models). Then the different stiffness matrixes of the classical lamination theory are formed.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Nowadays computers are extensively used in every area of science and technology, to obtain fast and accurate results. Especially in matrix operations, computer calculations provide fast and precise results. This is also the basic goal of this study.

The software developed in this work has several easy to understand menus and new menus can be added to the program. With the help of this user-friendly program, persons with basic engineering background can easily make macromechanical calculations on fiber-reinforced composites.

References

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Appendix

